

RESEARCH ARTICLE

On The Inverse Function Theorem and its Generalization in the Unitary Space

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ABSTRACT

It is obvious that the inverse function theorem holds in the Banach space for R . In my paper on the generalized inverse function theorem, it was observed that the inverse function theorem also holds for R^n . However, in this paper, I attempted to establish that it holds in the unitary space and consequently can be extended to C^n ; the generalized unitary space.

Key words: Norm space, continuity, differentiability, inverse function theorem

THE INVERSE FUNCTION THEOREM IN R

A function F could fail to be one to one but may be so on a subset S of D_F and by this we mean that $F(X_1)$ and $F(X_2)$ are distinct, whenever X_1 and X_2 are distinct points of S . Hence, F is not invertible but when F_S is defined on S by $F_S(X) = F(X), X \in S$, and left undefined for $X \notin S$ then F_S is invertible. We say that F_S is the restriction of F to S and that F_S^{-1} is the inverse of F restricted to S . The domain of F_S^{-1} is $F(S)$. If F is one to one on a neighborhood of X_0 , we say that F is locally invertible on X_0 and if this true for every X_0 in a set S , we say that F is locally invertible on S .

Definition 1.1: [Riez [8]], [Williams[10]] A function $F: R^n \rightarrow R^n$ is regular on an open set S if F is one to one and continuously differentiable on S and $JF(X) \neq 0$, if $X \in S$. Also we may say that F is regular on an arbitrary set S if F is regular on an open set containing S .

Theorem 1.1: [Athanasius[1]], [Erwin[6]] Suppose that $F: R^n \rightarrow R^n$ is regular on an open set S , and let $G = F_S^{-1}$ then $F(S)$ is open, G is continuously

differentiable on $F(S)$ and $G'(U) = F'(X)^{-1}$, where $U = F(X)$.

Moreover, since G is one to one on $F(S)$, G is regular on $F(S)$.

Definition 1.2: If F is regular on an open set S , we say that F_S^{-1} is a branch of F^{-1} . Hence, it is possible to better define a branch of F^{-1} on a set $T \subset R(F)$ if and only if $T = F(S)$ where F is regular on S . Note that any subset of $R(F)$ that does not have this property cannot have a branch of F^{-1} defined on them.

Theorem 1.2 (the inverse function theorem) [Athanasius[1]], [Erwin[6]]: Let $F: R^n \rightarrow R^n$ be continuously differentiable on an open set S and suppose that $JF(X) \neq 0$ on S . Then, if $X_0 \in S$, there is an open neighborhood N of X_0 on which F is regular. Moreover, $F(N)$ is open and $G = F_N^{-1}$ is continuously differentiable on $F(N)$ with $G'(U) = [F'(X)]^{-1}$ (where $U = F(X), U \in F(N)$).

Corollary 1.3: If F is continuously differentiable on a neighborhood of X_0 and $JF(X_0) \neq 0$, then there is an open neighborhood N of X_0 on which the conclusion of theorem 1.2 holds.

THE INVERSE FUNCTION THEOREM ON THE UNITARY SPACE

Here, we discuss the inverse function theorem in a plane other than the reals and in precise the

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unitary space C^n . As preliminary in this section, we introduce the following concepts.

Local invertibility

A complex function F is one to one only on a subset S of D_F where D_F is complex points. This in general may fail but that the assertion holds means that $F(Z_1)$ and $F(Z_2)$ are distinct, whenever Z_1 and Z_2 are distinct points of S so that F is not invertible except if F_s is defined on S by $F_s(Z) = F(Z), Z \in S$,

Then, F_s is invertible. On the other hand, F_s is the restriction of F to S and F_s^{-1} is the inverse of F restricted to S and the domain of F_s^{-1} is $F(S)$. If F is one to one on a neighborhood of Z_0 , we say that F is locally invertible at Z_0 . If this is true for every Z_0 in a set S , then F is locally invertible on S .

Regular invertible functions

Definition 2.2.1: A complex function $F: C^n \rightarrow C^n$ is regular on an open set S and let $G = F_s^{-1}$. Then, $F(S)$ is open, G is continuously differentiable on $F(S)$ and $G(U) = (F(z))^{-1}$, where $U = F(Z)$. Moreover, since G is one to one on $F(S)$, G is regular on $F(S)$.

Definition 2.2.2: We say that F_s^{-1} is a branch of F^{-1} if F is regular on an open set S . More so, this definition implies that F_s^{-1} is a branch of F^{-1} on a set $T \subset C(F)$ if and only if $T = F(S)$, where F is regular on S . Note that any open subset of $C(F)$ that does not have this property cannot be said to have a branch defined on it.

Theorem 2.2 (the inverse function theorem): Let $F: C^n \rightarrow C^n$ be continuously differentiable on an open set S and suppose that $JF(Z) \neq 0$ on S . Then, if $Z_0 \in S$, then there is an open neighborhood N of Z_0 on which F is regular. More so, $F(N)$ is open and $G = F_N^{-1}$ is continuously differentiable on $F(N)$, with $G'(N) = [F'(z)]^{-1}$ (where $U = F(Z)$), $U \in F(N)$.

Corollary 2.2.3: If F is continuously differentiable on a neighborhood of Z_0 and $JF(Z_0) \neq 0$, then

there is an open neighborhood N of Z_0 on which the conclusion of theorem 2.2 holds.

GENERALIZED INVERSE FUNCTION THEOREM IN THE UNITARY SPACE

Generalized local invertibility

A set of complex functions F_i are/is one to one only on a subset S of D_{F_i} where D_{F_i} is complex points. This in general may fail but that the assertion holds mean that $F_i(z_1)$ and $F_i(z_2)$ are distinct points of S so that F_i is not invertible except F_i is defined on S by $F_i(z_i) = F_i(z_i)$, $z_i \in S$ and left undefined for $z_i \in S$ and then F_i is invertible.

On the other hand, F_i is restrictions of F_i to S and F_i^{-1} is the inverses of F_i 's restricted to S and the domain of F_i^{-1} is $F(S)$. If F_i 's is one to one z_0 neighborhoods, we say that F_i 's is locally invertible each at z_0 . If this is true for every z_0 in a set S , then F_i 's is locally invertible on S .

Generalized regular invertible functions

Definition 3.2.1: Complex functions $F_i: C^n \rightarrow C^n$ are each regular on an open set S and $J_i F_i(z_i) \neq 0$ if $z_i \in S$. We also say that F_i 's is each regular on an arbitrary set S if F_i 's is regular on an open set containing S .

Theorem 3.2.1. Suppose that $F_i: C^n \rightarrow C^n$ are regular on an open set S and if $G_i = F_i^{-1}$, then $F_i(S)$ is open and G_i 's is continuously differentiable on $F_i(S)$ while $G_i(U) = (F_i(z_i))^{-1}$, where $U_i = F_i(z_i)$. Moreover, since G_i 's is one to one on $F_i(S)$, G_i 's irregular on $F_i(S)$.

Definition 3.2: We say that F_i^{-1} is branches of F_i^{-1} if F_i is regular on an open set S . More so, this definition implies that F_i 's is branches of F_i^{-1} on a $T_i \subset R(F_i)$ if and only if $T_i = F_i(S)$, where F_i 's is regular on S . Note that any open subsets of $R(F_i)$ that do not have this property cannot be said to have branches defined on them.

MAIN RESULTS

Theorem 3.2 [the generalized inverse function theorem in the unitary space]

Let $F_i : C^n \rightarrow C^n$ be a set of continuously differentiable functions on an open set S . Suppose that each $J_i F_i(z_i) \neq 0$ on S . Then, if $z_i \in S$, there are open neighborhoods N_i of z_i on which F_i 's is regular. More so, $F_i(N_i)$ is each open with

$$F(N) = \bigcup_{j=1}^n \{F_j(N_j)\}$$

and

$$G = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \{G_i\} = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \{F_{i_{N_i}}\} = F_N^{-1}$$

Continuously differentiable on $\bigcup_{i=1}^n \{F_i(N_i)\}$ such

$$\text{that } G'(N) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \{G_i(N_i)\} = \left[\bigcup_{i=1}^n \{F_i(z_i)\} \right]^{-1}$$

$$\text{where } \bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i = \bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(z_i), \bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i \in \bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(N_i).$$

Proof: First, we show that if $X_0 \in S$, then a neighborhood of $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(X_0)$ is in $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(S)$. This implies that $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(S)$ is open.

Since S is open, there is a $\bigcup_{i=1}^n \rho_i > 0$ such that

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n B_{\rho_i}(X_0) \subset S. \text{ Let } \bigcup_{i=1}^n B_i \text{ be the boundary of } \bigcup_{i=1}^n B_{\rho_i}(X_0), \text{ thus}$$

$$B = \bigcup_{i=1}^n B_i = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \{X_i\} \bigcup_{i=1}^n X_i - X_0 = \bigcup_{i=1}^n p_i = p \tag{3.1}$$

The functions

$$\sigma = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \sigma_i(X_i) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(X_i) - F_i(X_0)$$

are continuous on S and therefore on $\bigcup_{i=1}^n B_i$

which is compact. Hence, there is a point $\bigcup_{i=1}^n X_i$ in $\bigcup_{i=1}^n B_i$ where $\bigcup_{i=1}^n \sigma_i(X_i)$ attain its minimum

value say, $\bigcup_{i=1}^n m_i$ on $\bigcup_{i=1}^n B_i$. Moreover, $\bigcup_{i=1}^n m_i > 0$

since $\bigcup_{i=1}^n Z_i \neq 0$ each $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i$ is one to one on S .

Therefore, $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F(Z_i) - F(Z_0) \geq \bigcup_{i=1}^n m_i > 0$ if

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n Z_i - Z_0 = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \rho_i \tag{3.2}$$

The set

$$\left\{ \bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i - F_i(Z_0) \leq \bigcup_{i=1}^n \frac{m_i}{2} \right\}$$

is a neighborhood of $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(Z_0)$.

We will show that it is a subset of $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(S)$. To

see this, let $\bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i$ be a set of fixed points in this set. Thus,

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i - F_i(Z_i) < \bigcup_{i=1}^n \frac{m_i}{2} \tag{3.3}$$

Consider the function

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n \sigma_i(Z_i) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i - F_i(Z_i)^2$$

which is continuous on S . Note that $\bigcup_{i=1}^n \sigma_i \geq \bigcup_{i=1}^n \frac{m_i}{4}$ if

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n Z_i - Z_0 = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \rho_i$$

Since if $\bigcup_{i=1}^n Z_i - Z_0 = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \rho_i$, then

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i - F_i(Z_i) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n (U_i - F_i(Z_0)) + \begin{pmatrix} F_i(Z_0) \\ -F_i(Z_i) \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\geq \bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(X_0) - F_i(X_i) - \bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i - F_i(X_0) \geq$$

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n \left(m_i - \frac{m_i}{2} \right) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n \frac{m_i}{2}$$

that is, from Equations (3.2) and (3.3).

Since $\bigcup_{i=1}^n \sigma_i$ is continuous on S , $\bigcup_{i=1}^n \sigma_i$ attains a minimum value μ on the compact set $\overline{B_\rho(Z_0)}$ that is there are $\overline{Z_i}$ in $\overline{B_\rho(Z_0)}$ such that

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n \sigma_i(Z_i) \geq \bigcup_{i=1}^n \sigma_i(\overline{Z_i}) = \mu, \bigcup_{i=1}^n Z_i \in \overline{B_\rho(Z_0)} \tag{3.4}$$

Setting

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n Z_i = Z_0,$$

We conclude from Equation (3.3) that

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n \sigma_i(\bar{Z}) = \mu \leq \bigcup_{i=1}^n \sigma_i(Z_0) < \bigcup_{i=1}^n \frac{m_i}{4}$$

Because of Equations (3.1) and (3.4), this rules out

the possibility that $\bigcup_{i=1}^n Z_i \in B$, so $\bigcup_{i=1}^n \bar{Z}_i \in B_\rho(Z_0)$.

Now, we want to show that $\mu = 0$; that is

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i = \bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(\bar{Z}_i)$$

To this end, we note that $\bigcup_{i=1}^n \sigma_i(Z_i)$ can be written as

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n \sigma_i(Z_i) = \sum_{i=1}^n (U_{i,j} - f_{i,j}(Z_i))^2$$

So $\bigcup_{i=1}^n \sigma_i$ is differentiable on $B_\rho(Z_0)$. Therefore,

the first partial derivatives of $\bigcup_{i=1}^n \sigma_i$ are all zero at

the local minimum point $\bigcup_{i=1}^n \bar{Z}_i$, so

$$\sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\partial f_{i,j}(\bar{Z})}{\partial x_{i,j}} (U_{i,j} - f_{i,j}(\bar{Z})) = 0 \text{ for } 1 \leq i \leq n$$

or in matrix form

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n F'_i(\bar{Z}_i) (U_i - F_i(\bar{Z}_i)) = 0$$

Since $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F'_i(Z_i)$ is non-singular, this implies that

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i = \bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(\bar{Z}_i)$$

Thus, we have shown that every U that satisfies

(3.3) is in $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(S)$ is open.

Next, we show that $\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i$ is continuous on

$\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(S)$ and Z_0 is the unique point in S such that

$\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(Z_0) = U_0$. Since $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F'_i(Z_0)$ is invertible,

there exists $\lambda_i > 0$ and an open neighborhood

$\bigcup_{i=1}^n N$ of Z_0 such that $\bigcup_{i=1}^n N \subset S$ and

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(Z_i) - F_i(Z_0) \geq \bigcup_{i=1}^n \lambda_i Z_i - Z_0 \text{ if } \bigcup_{i=1}^n Z_i \in \bigcup_{i=1}^n N_i \tag{3.5}$$

Since $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i$ satisfies the hypothesis of the

present theorem on $\bigcup_{i=1}^n N_i$, the first part of

this proof shows that $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(N_i)$ is an open set

containing $U_i = \bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(Z_0)$. Therefore, there is

a $\delta > 0$ such that $\bigcup_{i=1}^n Z_i = \bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_i)$ is in $\bigcup_{i=1}^n N_i$

if $\bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i \in B_\delta(U_0)$. Setting $\bigcup_{i=1}^n Z_i = \bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_i)$ and

$Z_0 = \bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_0)$ in Equation (3.5), yields

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(G_i(U_i)) - F_i(G_i(U_0)) \geq \bigcup_{i=1}^n \lambda_i G_i(U_i) - G_i(U_0)$$

if $\bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i \in B_\delta(U_0)$

Since $\bigcup_{i=1}^n [F_i(G_i(U_i))] = \bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i$, this can be written as

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_i) - G_i(U_0) \leq \bigcup_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\lambda} U_i - U_0$$

If

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i \in B_\delta(U_0) \tag{3.6}$$

which means that $\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i$ is continuous at U_0 . Since

U_0 is an arbitrary point in $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(S)$, it follows

that $\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i$ is continuous on $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F(S)$. We will

now show that $\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i$ is different at U_0 .

Since

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n [G_i(F_i(Z_i))] = \bigcup_{i=1}^n Z_i, Z_i \in S$$

The chain rule implies that if $\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i$ is differentiable at U_0 , then

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i'(U_0) F_i'(Z_0) = I$$

Therefore, if $\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i$ is differentiable at U_0 , the differentiable matrix of $\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i$ must be

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i'(U_0) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n [F_i'(X_0)]^{-1}$$

So to show that $\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i$ is differentiable at U_0 , we must show that if

$$\begin{aligned} & \bigcup_{i=1}^n H_i(U_i) \\ & \qquad \qquad \qquad G_i(U_i) \\ & = \frac{\bigcup_{i=1}^n \left(\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_i) - \bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_0) - \bigcup_{i=1}^n [F_i'(Z_0)]^{-1} \bigcup_{i=1}^n (U_i - U_0) \right)}{\bigcup_{i=1}^n |U_i - U_0|} \end{aligned}$$

For

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i \neq U_0 \tag{3.7}$$

Then,

$$\lim_{U_i \rightarrow U_0} \bigcup_{i=1}^n H_i(U_i) = 0 \tag{3.8}$$

Since $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i$ is one to one on S and

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i'(G_i(U_i)) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i, \text{ it follows that } \bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i \neq U_0,$$

then $\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_i) \neq \bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_0)$. Therefore, we can multiply the numerator and denominator of

Equation (3.7) by $\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_i) - G_i(U_0)$ to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \bigcup_{i=1}^n H_i(U_i) &= \frac{\bigcup_{i=1}^n |G_i(U_i) - G_i(U_0)|}{\bigcup_{i=1}^n |U_i - U_0|} \\ & \left(\frac{\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_i) - \bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_0) - \bigcup_{i=1}^n [F_i'(Z_0)]^{-1} \bigcup_{i=1}^n (U_i - U_0)}{\bigcup_{i=1}^n |G_i(U_i) - G_i(U_0)|} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{\bigcup_{i=1}^n |G_i(U_i) - G_i(U_0)|}{\bigcup_{i=1}^n |U_i - U_0|} [F_i'(Z_0)]^{-1}$$

$$\left(\frac{\bigcup_{i=1}^n (U_i - U_0) - F_i'(Z_0) (\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_i) - \bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_0))}{\bigcup_{i=1}^n |G_i(U_i) - G_i(U_0)|} \right)$$

If $0 < \bigcup_{i=1}^n |U_i - U_0| < \delta$. Because of Equation (3.6), this implies

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\lambda_1} \left\| [F_i'(Z_0)]^{-1} \right\| \\ & \left\| \frac{\bigcup_{i=1}^n (U_i - U_0) - F_i'(Z_0) (\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_i) - \bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_0))}{\bigcup_{i=1}^n |G_i(U_i) - G_i(U_0)|} \right\| \\ & \bigcup_{i=1}^n |H_i(U_i)| \leq \bigcup_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_i) - \bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_0)}{\bigcup_{i=1}^n |G_i(U_i) - G_i(U_0)|} \right| \end{aligned}$$

If

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n |U_i - U_0| < \delta$$

Now let

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n H_{i,j}(U_i) = \frac{\bigcup_{i=1}^n (U_i - U_0) - \bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i'(X_0) (\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_i) - \bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_0))}{\bigcup_{i=1}^n |G_i(U_i) - G_i(U_0)|}$$

To complete the proof of Equation (3.8), we must show that $\lim_{U_i \rightarrow U_0} \bigcup_{i=1}^n H_{i,j}(U_i) = 0$. Since $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i$ is differentiable at Z_0 we know that if

$$\begin{aligned} \bigcup_{i=1}^n H_{i,k}(Z_i) &= \lim_{Z_i \rightarrow Z_0} \bigcup_{i=1}^n H_{i,j}(U_i) \\ & \qquad \qquad \qquad F_i(Z_0) \\ & = \frac{\bigcup_{i=1}^n (F_i(Z_i) - \bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i'(Z_0) (Z - Z_0))}{\bigcup_{i=1}^n |Z - Z_0|} \end{aligned} \tag{3.9}$$

Then,

$$\lim_{Z_i \rightarrow Z_0} H_{i,k}(Z_i) = 0$$

Since $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(G_i(U_i)) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i$ and

$$Z_0 = \bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(U_0)$$

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n (H_{i,j}(U_i)) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n (H_{i,k}(G_i(U_i)))$$

Now, suppose for $\varepsilon > 0, \exists \delta_j > 0 \bigcup_{i=1}^n |H_{i,k}(Z_i)| < \varepsilon$, if

$$0 < \bigcup_{i=1}^n |Z_i - X_0| = \bigcup_{i=1}^n |Z_i - G_i(U_0)| < \delta_j$$

Since $\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i$ is continuous at U_0 , there is a

$\delta_{i,k} \in (0, \delta)$ such that

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n |G_i(U_i) - G_i(U_0)| < \delta_j$$

if

$$0 < \bigcup_{i=1}^n |U_i - U_0| < \delta_{i,k}$$

This and Equation (3.11) imply that

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n |H_{i,k}(U_i)| = \bigcup_{i=1}^n |H_{i,k}G_i(U_i)| < \varepsilon$$

$$\text{If } 0 < \bigcup_{i=1}^n |U_i - U_0| < \delta_{i,k}$$

Since this implies (3.9), $\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i$ is differentiable at X_0 .

Since U_0 is an arbitrary member of $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(N_i)$, we can now drop the zero subscript and conclude

that $\bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i$ is continuous and differentiable on

$\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(N_i)$, and

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n [G'_i(U_i)] = \bigcup_{i=1}^n [F'_i(Z_i)]^{-1}, \bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i \in \bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(N_i)$$

Hence,

$$G'(N) = \bigcup_{i=1}^n G_i(N_i) = \left[\bigcup_{i=1}^n \{F_i(Z_i)\} \right]^{-1}$$

Where

$$\bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i = \bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(Z_i), \bigcup_{i=1}^n U_i \in \bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i(N_i)$$

and hence the proof

Corollary 3.3: If $\bigcup_{i=1}^n F_i$ is continuously differentiable on a neighborhood of Z_0 and $\bigcup_{i=1}^n J_i F_i(Z_0) \neq 0$, then, there is an open neighborhood $\bigcup_{i=1}^n N_i$ of Z_0 on which the conclusion of the main result holds.

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